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⚡ . > ⊕ Assimilation of snow depth in ERA5

Assimilation of snow depth in ERA5 (CUS-24363)

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ACTIVITY

Your request status changed to: **Answered and Closed** 25/Jun/24 2:52 PM **LATEST**

Kevin Marsh 25/Jun/24 2:52 PM

Dear Gabriel,

Glad we could help, I will close this query now.

Should you need further assistance, please don't hesitate to contact us again using our [Support Portal](#) or if you are a CDS user, give a try to our [Knowledge Duck](#), our Virtual Assistant on the Climate Data Store (CDS).

We post **announcements** on our [forum](#) where you may also interact with other users at any time about our products and services.

We also recommend users to regularly check the [CDS](#) and [ADS](#) websites for additional news or reported known issues on datasets or services.

Kind regards,

Kevin

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ANSWERED AND CLOSED

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REQUEST PARTICIPANTS

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Gabriel
Stachura
Creator

Your request status changed to: **With Specialist Support** 29/May/24 2:27 PM

Gabriel Stachura 29/May/24 2:27 PM

Dear Alison,

That's great - thank you so much <3. The issue can be closed.

Your request status changed to: **Specialist Support waiting for your reply** 29/May/24 12:43 PM

Alison Cobb 29/May/24 12:43 PM

Dear Gabriel,

I confirm that snow-depth observations from the area of Poland, Czech Republic and Slovakia comes only from SYNOP stations.

Kind Regards,

Alison

Your request status changed to: **With Specialist Support** 07/Mar/24 12:26 PM

Gabriel Stachura 07/Mar/24 12:26 PM

Dear Alison,

indeed, I found a list of parameters used as a forcing to ERA5-Land, thank you. However, regarding the details of data assimilation, I am still not satisfied with what I found in the IFS documentation. Maybe it was too demanding from my site to ask for a list of stations, but are you able to anyhow narrow the following statement from the IFS documentation (data assimilation):

*Snow depth observations include conventional snow depth reports from SYNOP stations as well as **additional national snow depth observations***

reported by several member states and available on the GTS

The sentence is followed by a citation of *de Rosnay et al., 2011b, 2014, 2015*, which indeed provides some more details (e.g. mentions some countries that do provide additional snow depth measurements), but this regards to cy40, so the question is was it the same during production of ERA5? Or maybe I should put the question directly to the land data assimilation team of ECMWF, it this is possible?

Thank you in advance for you reply!

Your request status changed to: **Specialist Support**
waiting for your reply 05/Mar/24 3:59 PM

Alison Cobb 05/Mar/24 3:59 PM

Dear Gabriel,

Many thanks for your email. Regarding your first question on the variables in ERA5-Land, you will find this detailed information in the ERA5-Land documentation.

Unfortunately, we are unable to provide you with the station details that you have requested, however, the IFS documentation covers how snow depth observations are handled.

Kind Regards,

Alison

Muñoz-Sabater, J., Dutra, E., Agustí-Panareda, A., Albergel, C., Arduini, G., Balsamo, G., Boussetta, S., Choulga, M., Harrigan, S., Hersbach, H. and Martens, B., 2021. ERA5-Land: A state-of-the-art global reanalysis dataset for land applications. *Earth system science data*, 13(9), pp.4349-4383.

Your request status changed to: **With Specialist**

Support 09/Feb/24 3:56 PM

Your request status changed to: **Under investigation** 08/Feb/24 10:06 AM

Kevin Marsh 08/Feb/24 10:06 AM

Dear Gabriel

Thank you for your enquiry to ECMWF Support.

We will investigate and get back to you as soon as possible

Kind regards,

Kevin

ECMWF Support

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Your request status changed to: **Waiting for Support** 08/Feb/24 8:06 AM

Your request status changed to: **Waiting for 2nd Line** 08/Feb/24 7:37 AM

Your request status changed to: **Under investigation** 08/Feb/24 7:37 AM

Description

I would kindly ask for more information about assimilation of snow depth in ERA5 reanalysis (hourly data, deterministic run). Also, I am interested in which variables are passed from ERA5 to ERA5-Land as a forcing. From the documentation of ERA5-Land I learned that ERA5-Land has no data assimilation and observations are indirectly passed through a forcing from ERA5 (which do has DA). My first question is: which variables exactly are involved in the forcing - are there only atmospheric fields or are there any land-surface variables (e.g. some snow fields)?

And from the documentation of ERA5 (which links to the documentation of IFS CY41R2) I found out that snow analysis is created from snow-depth observations, snow depth background field and the satellite snow-extent product. And that conventional observations come from SYNOP reports and "additional national snow depth observations reported by several member states and available on the GTS". My second request, therefore, can you tell whether the snow-depth observations from the area of Poland, Czech Republic and Slovakia comes only from SYNOP stations or some lower-ranked stations are also involved? Can you provide me a list of those stations? And, if there are SYNOP stations constantly excluded from DA (e.g. some mountainous stations), can you also list them?

Request created

08/Feb/24 7:37 AM